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Prevalence of infectious and non-infectious diseases in cattle population in Moulvibazar district of Bangladesh

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Abstract

Infectious and non-infectious diseases of cattle cause great economic losses of farmers as well as country every year by reducing growth, production and mortality of cattle population. The objective of this research work was to find out the prevalence of infectious and non-infectious diseases of cattle at Moulvibazar, Sylhet, Bangladesh. A total of 2285 clinical cases were diagnosed at District Veterinary Hospital in Moulvibazar, Bangladesh during January to June, 2016. Disease diagnosis was made on the basis of owner's statement, physical examination, clinical signs, gross pathology, and laboratory procedures. Data were analysed to determine disease prevalence in cattle with related to breed and sex. Diagnosed diseases were categorised as infectious diseases, parasitic disease, digestive disorder, respiratory disorder, reproductive disorder, metabolic disorder and other diseases. According to our result the highest prevalence was shown for parasitic diseases (49.32%) followed by digestive disorder (25.64%), other diseases (10.77%), Infectious Diseases (9.28%), respiratory disorders (2.32%), reproductive disorders (1.88%) and metabolic disorders (0.79%). The prevalence of diseases in male (53.57%) which includes infectious diseases (4.90%), parasitic diseases (30.55%), digestive disorders (12.30%), respiratory disorders (0.79%) and others (5.03%). Local bred of cattle were more susceptible to diseases as prevalence was 57.46% followed by Cross-bred (36.58%) and Red Chittagong (5.96%). The prevalence of diseases in male (53.57%) was higher than in female (46.43%). Our study on prevalence of infectious and non-infectious diseases of cattle in Moulvibazar district of Bangladesh provides necessary information to take proper strategies for control and prevention of diseases.

Keywords: Prevalence, Infectious, Non-infectious, Cattle, Bangladesh

INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh is a densely populated and agriculture based country in the world. Livestock sector plays very important role to fulfil the protein requirement as well promoting financial condition of people. There are about 23.785 million cattle, 1.471 million buffalo, 25.766 million goat, 3.335 million sheep, 268.393 million chicken and 52.240 million duck in Bangladesh (DLS, 2016). Contribution of Livestock in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) 1.66%, GDP growth rate of livestock 3.21% and share of livestock in agricultural GDP 14.21% (DLS, 2016). Malnutrition and diseases are the main cause of weak emaciation and non-satisfactory productive performance of the animals (Badruzzaman et al. 2015). Anthrax, foot and mouth disease, haemorrhagic septicaemia etc. are considered as endemic diseases in Bangladesh (Mondal et al. 2014). Huge economic loss in livestock sector occurs due parasitic infestation of cattle (Sardar et al. 2006). It is reported that reproductive disorders have great impact on economic losses to the dairy farmers in Bangladesh (Talukder et al. 2005). In Bangladesh, traditional management system and feeding habit of animals and geographical location act as favourable causes for incidence of different diseases described by Paul et al.(2011) and Lucky et al.(2016). Besides, variation in the age, breed and sex of animals, seasons and farming system greatly influence the incidence of diseases in livestock animals including cattle described by Alim et al.(2012), Sarker et al.(2011) and Sultana et al.(2008). Impact of climate change plays a major role to influence the disease occurrence in Bangladesh discussed by Chowdhury et al.(2016).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area and study period

The study was carried out at District veterinary hospital, Moulvibazar, Bangladesh to determine the prevalence of infectious and non-infectious diseases in Moulvibazar. A total of 2285 clinical cases of cattle of different breed and sex were diagnosed during the period from January to June of 2016.

2.2 Diagnosis of diseases

The diseases were diagnosed by physical examination, clinical signs, gross pathology, and laboratory procedures. In the procedures of physical examination behaviour, physical condition, pulse, respiration, body temperature, posture, gait, salivation, enlargement of the abdomen, defecation, instability of locomotion of animals were observed by visual examination and were recorded. Disease history was taken into consideration while performing general physical examination. Examination of different parts and structure of the body of sick animals were performed by palpation, percussion, auscultation, needle puncture and movement of the affected animals. Bacterial, viral, and fungal diseases were diagnosed specifically on the basis of specific clinical signs and gross lesions (Jones et al. 1996). Mastitis was diagnosed on the basis of history and physical abnormalities of udder (Radostits et al. 2007). Parasitic infestations were diagnosed by faeces examination under microscope (Soulsby, 1986). Diagnosed diseases were categorised as infectious disease, parasitic disease, digestive disorder, respiratory disorder, metabolic disease and other diseases for statistical analysis.

2.3. Data Analysis

Table-1: Prevalence of diseases and disorders in cattle

Disease categories	Disease/Disorder	Affected Cattle No. (n=2285)	Percent Prevalence	Prevalence (%) by categories
Infectious disease	Foot and mouth disease	140	6.13	9.28(212)
	Black quarter	21	0.92	
	Mastitis	48	2.10	
	Hemorrhagic septicemia	1	0.04	
	Wart	2	0.09	
Parasitic disease	Babesiosis	6	0.26	49.32(1127)
	Anaplasmosis	9	0.39	
	Coccidiosis	26	1.14	
	Fasioliasis	477	20.88	
	Hump sore	41	1.80	
	Balantidiasis	23	1.00	
	Strongyloidiasis	58	2.54	
	Paramphistomiasis	194	8.49	
Digestive disorder	Ectoparasite	293	12.82	25.64(586)
	Non-specific diarrhea	175	7.66	
	Anorexia	110	4.81	
	Simple indigestion	88	3.85	
	Malnutrition	201	8.79	
Respiratory disorder	Colic	12	0.53	2.32(53)
	Pneumonia	50	2.19	
Metabolic disorder	Nasal granuloma	3	0.13	0.79(18)
	Milk fever	18	0.79	
Reproductive disorder	Placental retention	16	0.70	1.88(43)
	Uterine prolapse	4	0.17	
	Dystocia	8	0.35	
	Anestrus	15	0.66	
Others	Dog Bite	10	0.44	10.77(246)
	Arthritis	24	1.05	
	Fracture	13	0.57	
	Lacrimation	3	0.13	
	Non-specific fever	108	4.73	
	Wound	88	3.85	
Total		2285	100	100(2285)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 2285 different clinical cases were diagnosed and registered at District Veterinary Hospital, Moulvibazar during the study period of January to June, 2016. The diseases were categorized as infectious disease, parasitic disease, digestive disorder, respiratory disorder, reproductive disorder, metabolic disorder and other diseases. The highest prevalence was shown for parasitic diseases (49.32%) and the lowest prevalence was shown for metabolic disorder (0.79%) (Table-1). Among the other categories, prevalence of digestive disorder (25.64%) was significantly higher. Local breed was more susceptible to diseases comparing with cross breed and Red Chittagong (Table-2). Males were more susceptible to diseases than females (table-3).

The prevalence of infectious diseases was 9.28% which consisted of foot and mouth disease (6.13%), black quarter (0.92%), mastitis (2.10%), hemorrhagic septicemia (0.04%) and wart (0.09%) (Table-1). Our result is similar to the result of Badruzzaman et al. (2015) who reported the prevalence of infectious diseases of cattle in Chittagong district of Bangladesh as 9.49%. Among the infectious diseases, highest prevalence was found in foot and mouth disease (6.13%) which was significantly lower than Sarker et al. (2011) who reported the prevalence of foot and mouth disease of cattle in Rajshahi district of Bangladesh as 25.07%. In our study prevalence of mastitis (2.10%) was slightly higher than the report of Hossain et al. (2016) that was 1.15%. The prevalence of infectious diseases were 4.51%, 3.76% and 1.01% respectively in the local, cross and Red Chittagong bred (Table-2). Males (4.90%) were more susceptible to infectious diseases than females (4.38%) (Table-3). Our results oppose to the result of Badruzzaman et al. (2015) who reported female (5.13%) were more susceptible than male (4.36%).

Highest prevalence (49.32%) was recorded in parasitic disease that constituted of babesiosis (0.26%), anaplasmosis (0.39%), coccidiosis (1.14%), fascioliasis (20.88%), hump sore (1.80%), balantidiasis (1.00%), strongyloidiasis (2.54%), paramphistomiasis (8.49%) and ectoparasite (12.82%) (Table-1). Our result of parasitic disease was higher than prevalence recorded (12.4%) in Mohammadpur, Magura (Karim et al. 2014). In parasitic disease category, highest prevalence was recorded in fascioliasis (20.88%) which was lower than the result of Ghosh et al. (2016) who reported as 25.88%. Among protozoan parasites, highest prevalence was found in coccidiosis (1.14%) followed by balantidiasis (1.00%), anaplasmosis (0.39%), babesiosis (0.26%). Mahmud et al. (2015) reported the prevalence of babesiosis in Sirajganj district of Bangladesh as 2.27%. Parasitic diseases were higher prevalent in the local bred (30.15%) than cross bred (16.49%) and Red Chittagong (2.67%) (Table-2). Prevalence of parasitic diseases in males (30.55%) was higher than females (18.77%) (Table-3). Azam et al. (2017) found the prevalence of parasitic diseases in male as 19% and in female as 19.26% at Joypurhat.

Prevalence of digestive disorder was 25.64% of which malnutrition was 8.79% followed by non-specific diarrhea (7.66%), anorexia (4.81%), simple indigestion (3.85%) and colic (0.53%) (Table-1). This result was significantly lower than the result recorded by Pallab et al. (2012) who described the prevalence of digestive disease as 47.05%. In digestive disease category, our result on prevalence of simple indigestion is slightly lower than the report of Hossain et al. (2016) who found the prevalence of simple indigestion as 4.81% in Moulvibazar. Prevalence of digestive disorder was found as 14.14%, 10.11% and 1.40% in local, cross and Red Chittagong bred respectively (Table-2). Digestive disorder was found comparatively higher in females (13.35%) than in males (12.30%) (Table-3). Kabir et al. (2010) also found the higher prevalence of digestive disorder in female than in male in Ulipur upazila, kurigram district, Bangladesh.

The prevalence of respiratory disorder was recorded as 2.32% which comprised of pneumonia (2.19%) and nasal granuloma (0.13%) (Table-1). Our study result on prevalence of respiratory disorder was lower than the prevalence recorded (5.5%) by Rahman et al. (2012). Among the respiratory disorder, we found the prevalence of pneumonia (2.19%) which was slightly lower than Rahman et al. (2012) (5.1%). Prevalence of respiratory disorder was calculated as 1.53%, 0.66% and 0.13% in local, cross and Red Chittagong bred respectively (Table-2). Females (1.53%) were more susceptible than males (0.79%) (Table-3).

Among the total clinical cases lowest prevalence was recorded for metabolic disorder (0.79%) (Table-1) that found only in case of females (Table-3). This result is lower than the record of Ullah et al. (2015) who

mentioned the prevalence of metabolic disorder in Chittagong as 4.24%. Cross bred (0.66%) was more susceptible than Red Chittagong (0.09%) and Local bred (0.04%) (Table-2).

Prevalence of reproductive disorder was 1.88% which included placental retention (0.70%), uterine prolapse (0.17%), dystocia (0.35%) and anestrus (0.66%) (Table-1). Among the reproductive disorder, highest prevalence was found in case of placental retention (0.70%) which was lower than the report of Juli et al. (2015) (0.73%) and Sarder et al. (2015) (4.10%). Prevalence of anestrus (0.66%), dystocia (0.35%) and uterine prolapsed (0.17%) were lower than Maruf et al. (2012) who reported anestrus (5.1%), dystocia (1.0%) and uterine prolapse (0.4%) at Chittagong. The prevalence of reproductive disorder was higher in Local among three breeds. The prevalence reproductive diseases were found as 1.05%, 0.74%, and 0.09% in Local, Cross-bred and Red Chittagong respectively (Table-2). Reproductive disease occurrence was reported only in females (Table-3).

In other diseases category, overall diseases prevalence was 10.77% which consisted of dog bite (0.44%), arthritis (1.05%), fracture (0.57%), lacrimation (0.13%), non-specific fever (4.73%), and wound (3.85%) (Table-1). Studied prevalence of dog bite (0.44%) agrees with the prevalence recorded at Dinajpur district of Bangladesh by Juli et al., (2015). In other category of disease prevalence was 6.04%, 4.16% and 0.57% found in Local, Cross-bred and Red Chittagong cattle. (Table-2). Local bred are mostly allowed for free grazing in the field so that dog bite mostly prevalent in Local bred. In this category female were more susceptible than male as the prevalence in female were 5.73% and prevalence in male were 5.03% were recorded. (Table-3).

Table-2: Breed wise comparison of clinical prevalence of diseases and disorders in male and female cattle

Categories	Local	Percent prevalence	Cross bred	Percent prevalence	Red Chittagong	Percent prevalence
Infectious disease	103	4.51	86	3.76	23	1.01
Parasitic disease	689	30.15	377	16.49	61	2.67
Digestive disorder	323	14.14	231	10.11	32	1.40
Respiratory disorder	35	1.53	15	0.66	3	0.13
Metabolic disorder	1	0.04	15	0.66	2	0.09
Reproductive disorder	24	1.05	17	0.74	2	0.09
Others	138	6.04	95	4.16	13	0.57
Total	1313	57.46	836	36.58	136	5.96

Table-3: Sex wise comparison of clinical prevalence of diseases and disorders in male and female cattle

Sl. no.	Disease category (n=2285)	Male		Female	
		No.	Percentage (%)	No.	Percentage (%)
01	Infectious disease	112	4.90	100	4.38
02	Parasitic disease	698	30.55	429	18.77
03	Digestive disorder	281	12.30	305	13.35

04	Metabolic disorder	0	0	18	0.79
05	Respiratory disorder	18	0.79	35	1.53
06	Reproductive disorder	0	0	43	1.88
07	Others	115	5.03	131	5.73
	Total	1224	53.57	1061	46.43

CONCLUSION

Infectious and non-infectious diseases are the major problem for animal health and production performance of livestock specially cattle. The study shows incidence of infectious diseases, parasitic disease, digestive disorder, respiratory disorder, reproductive disorder, metabolic disorder and other diseases in moulvibazar region. Study reveals high incidence of parasitic disease as well as digestive disorder. Regular deworming programme should be taken to minimize parasitic infestation. Our study on prevalence of infectious and non-infectious diseases of cattle in Moulvibazar district of Bangladesh provides necessary information to take proper strategies for control and prevention of diseases.

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